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D4.4 Final report on the qualification activities

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Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (UNICT - Francesco Pappalardo). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to internal reviewers, for a final review and validation.

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Table of contents

1. Introduction (UNICT).....	3
1.1. Introduction on WP4	3
1.2. Description of the content of this deliverable.....	3
2. FAT applications (UNICT - UNIBO).....	3
2.1. Introduction.....	3
2.2. BoneStrength.....	4
2.3. UISS-TB.....	5
3. Qualification Advice Process (UNICT - UNIBO - MIM).....	4
3.1. Introduction.....	4
3.2. BoneStrength QA outcome (UNIBO).....	4
3.3. UISS-TB QA outcome (UNICT)	5
4. DAT applications (UNICT, Tue, KUL)	10
4.1. Introduction.....	8
4.2. UISS-MS (UNICT)	10
4.3. InSole (KUL)	11
4.4. AngioSupport (TUE).....	12
5. DAT applications qualification strategies (UNICT, UNIBO)	14
5.1. UISS-MS qualification strategy.....	8
5.2. InSole qualification strategy	8
5.3. AngioSupport qualification strategy.....	9
6. DAT Exploitation	9
7. Concluding remarks (All).....	11

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction on WP4

WP4's main target is to lower barrier B3 "No clear regulatory pathways", by pursuing the first qualification of new In Silico Trials methodologies to be used in the regulatory evaluation of new medical products. It also aims to explore new regulatory pathways enabled by the use of In Silico Trials for three main categories of medical products: medicinal products, medical devices, and advanced therapeutic medicinal products (ATMPs). To these aims, WP4's activities focused mainly on two aspects: on one side, WP4 has determined which technical standard to use to qualify the credibility of In Silico Trials solutions in Europe and for products other than medical devices. The main goal is to decide if it is sufficient to use the ASME VV40.2018 standard in Europe or if additional standardisation activities are necessary. To reach this achievement, we performed an exploratory activity toward the other standardisation bodies potentially involved (ISO, CEN), as well as toward EMA and at least one notified body. These activities will be exhaustively described in D4.1 - Guideline on model's credibility standards.

On the other side, WP4 members worked on the regulatory qualification of the two Fast Accreditation Track (FAT) applications released from WP2 at M06. BoneStrength and UISS-TB solutions both target medicinal products, so they were successfully submitted to EMA qualification advice process.

1.2. Description of the content of this deliverable

This deliverable aims to describe the outcomes of the qualification advice process for both FAT applications, BoneStrength and UISS-TB. Furthermore, the most promising qualification strategies for Deep Accreditation Track (DAT) solutions, UISS-MS, AngioSupport and InSole applications, are presented.

2. FAT applications

2.1. Introduction

The Fast Accreditation Track (FAT) included two solutions, BoneStrength (R1) and UISS-TB (R2), that were already in an advanced stage of development and validation. The FAT solutions also produced two validation collections (R12 and R13) that any other developer of solutions targeting the same application can use. As previously reported, WP4 submitted the requests for qualification opinion to the EMA, creating two processes (R20 and R21) that any future company will be able to follow, and optimisation processes for running in silico phase III clinical trials (R30) and to scale agent-based models (R32). Last, but not least their trajectory to commercial services informed a number of regulatory, policy, informational and education processes (R23 to R29).

Regarding exploitation routes, the FAT solutions reached TRL8 (Phase 3 clinical trial: efficacy on large cohort. Cost-benefit analysis, primary research for Health Technology Assessment) by M36, as expected the ISW consortium. For each solution the primary commercial exploiter (already indicated as ISW industrial partners for FAT solutions), the tentative business model (consulting, software-as-a-service, Original Equipment Manufacturer, software licensing, etc.), the prospective customer profile and market segment characteristics were identified. Any further details about the capitalization strategy and the IPR protection policies can be found in D8.2 - Report on Results' Exploitation.

3. Qualification Advice Process

3.1. Introduction

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) qualification process is a voluntary scientific pathway leading to either a Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP) Opinion or Scientific Advice on innovative methods or drug development tools. The process involves:

1. Presubmission phase: Applicant prepares data and submits to EMA.
2. Preparatory meeting: Teleconference between EMA and applicant to discuss methods, data, and objectives.
3. Start of the procedure: Evaluation begins when submitted documentation meets EMA standards.
4. Data evaluation: QT assesses data and generates a list of issues document.
5. Discussion meeting: Applicant discusses issues with QT and other parties.
6. SAWP review: QT prepares a draft report discussed in the SAWP plenary.
7. CHMP adoption: CHMP adopts Qualification Advice or discusses Qualification Opinion.
8. Public consultation (only for Qualification Opinion): Draft Qualification Opinion released for public consultation.
9. Adoption of the FINAL CHMP Qualification Opinion: CHMP adopts the Qualification Opinion.
10. Communication and training: Final CHMP Qualification Opinion and grounds for acceptance made publicly available. Training sessions/workshops organized periodically.

Partner Mimesis S.r.l. applied the entire process on behalf of the ISW consortium.

3.2. BoneStrength QA timeline and outcome

The Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BBCT) at the hip represents a digital twin technology which is able to estimate the risk of fracture at the femur for a subject. This is done by orchestrating 1) a stochastic mathematical model which, starting from the subject's height and weight, calculates possible forces acting at the hip due to a fall on the side and 2) a CT-based finite element model of the subject's femur which predicts the femur strength in all plausible femur poses. By comparing the force due to a fall and the force causing the fracture of the femur, the absolute risk of fracture at the time of the CT, named ARF0, can be extracted. In a retrospective clinical study (Bhattacharya et al., 2018; Aldieri et al., 2022), BBCT was demonstrated to be more accurate than the areal bone mineral density (aBMD) in the prediction of hip fractures. Therefore, BBCT was the object of a qualification advice request to EMA, which aimed to propose the in silico methodology as a new response variable to be used in clinical trials for antiresorptive treatments efficacy assessment instead of aBMD.

In light of the fact that some phase III clinical studies where BMD was considered as the primary endpoint could be found in CHMP assessment reports related to treatments which EMA granted market authorisation, the initial Context of Use (CoU) which we envisioned for BBCT was within Phase III clinical studies.

On 04/12/2021, the Applicant Mimesis S.r.l. requested qualification advice for BBCT-Hip. The submission contained the main briefing book document and two annexes. The first Annex contained a detailed description of BBCT technology, while the second contained BBCT technical validation carried out according to ASME V&V40-2018 technical standard. The main Briefing Book document was articulated into two main sections: the first one contained a general summary with background information motivating the rationale and the need

for the proposed methodology and describing it, and the second section contained four questions for EMA and the respective positions of the Applicant. The four questions posed are reported in the following:

Question 1: Does EMA agree that the definition of Biomarker as “A biological molecule found in blood, other body fluids, or tissues that can be used to follow body processes and diseases in humans and animals” can be broadened so as to include an in silico-based prediction and therefore that term Biomarker applies also to BBCT-hip ARF0?

Question 2: Does EMA agree that the Context of Use clearly describes how BBCT will be used to provide a new surrogate of the fracture endpoint in Phase II clinical Trials?

Question 3: Does the EMA agree that the proposed technical validation strategy is acceptable to assess the precision and accuracy of the for BBCT-hip methodology in predicting the absolute risk of proximal femur fracture?

Question 4: Does the EMA agree that the provided clinical validation plan for BBCT-hip is sufficient in supporting the qualification of the use of BBCT as surrogate of the fracture risk in clinical trials?

The clinical validation plan proposed in the fourth question in particular involved the conventional design used for any drug development biomarker, i.e., the concepts of construct validity, predictive capacity, and ability to detect change. The cohort on which such clinical validation was proposed was made up of around 100 patients selected according to specific inclusion and exclusion criteria within the HipOp collection available at partner Rizzoli Orthopaedic Institute including CT scans of the hip region originally collected for computer-aided preoperative planning of total hip replacement. Four of those had experienced a proximal femur fracture.

On February 10th, 2022, we had a preliminary informal meeting with the appointed Qualification team, who strongly suggested lowering the CoU to Phase II studies and framing it in greater detail. In particular, the Qualification Team stressed that Phase III clinical trials for antiresorptive treatments look at fracture incidence as the primary outcome, and that would not change. Hence, in light of the comments received, the CoU was thoroughly modified, positioning BBCT as a response variable for use in place of the aBMD in Phase II dose-response clinical studies.

The Briefing Book was subsequently resubmitted in its modified version, and the procedure started on the 3rd of April 2022.

On the 13th of May 2022, EMA sent the applicants a list of issues, including 11 issues to be discussed with the Qualification Team during the Discussion meeting and 7 to be addressed only in written form. Although most of the issues involved methodological and/or technical details to be clarified and better described, the most critical issues dealt with the clinical validation plan originally proposed, which was judged far from sufficient despite the reduced CoU proposed. After submitting the response to the issues document, a discussion meeting with the EMA Qualification Team took place on September 1st, 2022, where the issues and the proposed answers were discussed. The main points of debate were related to the clinical validation plan: a full-scale clinical trial was mandatory, according to EMA, for such an in silico methodology to be judged reliable enough to be used in the proposed CoU.

On the 15th of September 2022, the EMA Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use adopted the advice to be given to the Applicant. The European Medicines Agency (EMA) suggested to undertake a more stuffed clinical validation for the use of the Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BBCT)-Hip as a surrogate marker for fracture risk in clinical trials in order to fully meet the EMA's regulatory standards.

3.3. UISS-TB QA outcome

The preparation of the Briefing Book for UISS-TB-DR has been finalized by Q3 2022 when the required documentation for the Scientific Advice application in the EMA IRIS portal has been uploaded.

Hence, according to EMA timelines the proposed period for a preparatory meeting would be held within a month after submission, during which we would obtain preliminary feedback and/or any further request on

specific remarks from the EMA Scientific Officer, Coordinators and members of the Qualification Team. Then the final briefing document has been submitted and the real Evaluation Phase started.

On 26/09/2022, the Applicant Mimesis S.r.l. requested qualification advice for UISS-TB-DR. The submission contained the main briefing book document and three annexes. The first Annex contained the detailed description of UISS-TB-DR methodology, the second contained UISS-TB-DR the credibility assessment plan for the UISS-TB-DR methodology and the third contained the procedure for the generation of digital twins for the simulation of tuberculosis with UISS-TB-DR. The primary Briefing Book document was divided into two key sections. The initial section provided a comprehensive summary with background information, outlining the reasoning and necessity for the proposed methodology, and describing it in detail. The second section included four questions addressed to EMA, accompanied by the corresponding positions of the Applicant. The four questioned posed are reported in the following:

Question 1: Does EMA agree that the Context of Use clearly describes how UISS-TB-DR will be used to inform vaccine dose decision-making in phase IIa clinical trials dealing with pulmonary TB?

Question 2: Does EMA agree with the overall strategy in general, and the risk assessment in particular, that we propose to evaluate the validity of the UISS-TB-DR as an in silico methodology for the optimisation of dose-response phase IIa clinical trials?

Question 3: Does the EMA agree that the proposed credibility assessment plan is adequate to support the request for qualification of the UISS-TB-DR in silico methodology for the proposed context of use?

Question 4: Does the EMA agree that a qualitative research based on clinical meaningfulness could be proposed in the credibility assessment validation plan to provide a more in-depth understanding of the predictive capability of the computational model demonstrating the ability of the model to reproduce general pathophysiological behaviours in TB?). Does also the EMA agree that the same qualitative approach can be used to reinforce the credibility assessment of CoU-related evidence i.e., support the escalation dose of a in silico phase IIa trial?

The clinical validation plan proposed in the third question in particular, compared the circulating IFN- γ levels in TB patients treated with RUTI in an escalating dose trial, measured at various time points, against the dose-response curve predicted for a similar cohort of virtual patients. The primary metric for comparison was the predictive capacity of the model regarding IFN- γ Spot Forming Units. Given the model's focus on the same biomarker already utilised in such studies, the necessity for demonstrating construct validity or the evaluation of the Minimal Important Difference (MID) was deemed redundant. The clinical validation process involved data from a phase IIa, randomised, escalating dose clinical trial. This trial evaluated the safety, tolerability, and immunogenicity of three doses of the RUTI vaccine following a one-month treatment with isoniazid. Participants in the trial were randomised to receive either a placebo or one of the RUTI doses (5, 25, or 50 μ g), administered subcutaneously in the deltoid muscle area of alternate arms, with a 28-day gap between doses. Monitoring extended up to one month following the second RUTI inoculation. The validation process included a comprehensive examination of the test sample and conditions, focusing on the number and characteristics of the test samples used, along with precise measurements of the test conditions. The final stage of the validation involved an assessment of the model by analysing the Equivalency of Input Parameters and Output Comparison.

On November 22nd, 2022, we had a preliminary informal meeting with the appointed Qualification team, who strongly suggested narrowing the CoU. In particular, the current context of use was very broad and did not specify: 1) the stage of the disease (active, latent), 2) the type of vaccine platform (protein fusion, live attenuated, vector, whole-cell), 3) population (age, HIV infection etc), 4) resistance. Moreover, a request to substantiate the role of IFN-gamma as an established biomarker for therapeutic vaccine dose/regimen selection was made.

The Briefing Book was subsequently resubmitted in its modified version, and the procedure started on the 11th of April 2023.

On the 31st of July 2023, a list of issues was received by EMA, including 6 issues to be discussed with the Qualification Team during the Discussion meeting and 11 to be addressed only in written form. Although most of the arisen issues involved methodological and/or technical details to be clarified and better described, the most critical issues were:

- Assumption of Dose Levels: The CHMP notes that the assumption that the three-dose levels standard for prophylactic vaccines will be suitable for therapeutic vaccines is unsubstantiated. They advise labelling the products as 'immunotherapy medicinal products' to avoid confusion with traditional prophylactic vaccines.
- Dose Selection Complexity: The process of dose selection is highlighted as being more complex than just evaluating an intermediate dose, a minimum effective dose (MED), and a maximum tolerated dose (MTD) in phase 2 trials. The CHMP suggests that a more elaborate approach for dose selection and regimen might be more appropriate.
- Phase 2a Study and Dose Selection: There's an assumption that selecting a dose in the Phase 2a study is a crucial milestone. However, the CHMP views this phase as exploratory, primarily focusing on safety, immunogenicity, and characterising the dose/regimen response. They believe this assumption needs more explanation.
- IFN- γ as a Biomarker for Dose Selection: The CHMP questions the assumption that changes in circulating interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) over time can inform clinical dose selection for an immunotherapy in latent tuberculosis (TB). They point out that the connection between the time course of IFN- γ and clinically relevant endpoints, such as the incidence of active TB, is not yet substantiated and needs further evidence.

After the submission of the response to the issues document, a discussion meeting with the EMA Qualification Team took place on September 25th, 2023, where the issues and the proposed answers were discussed. The main points of debate were related to the context of use for which it was assumed that circulating interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) changes over time are established as the basis for clinical dose regimen selection. For EMA CHMP, the link between the time course of IFN- γ and the prevention of active TB disease still needs to be substantiated.

On the 21st of December 2023, the EMA Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use adopted the advice to be given to the Applicant. The European Medicines Agency (EMA) issued a letter of support for the Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis disease model (UISS-TB-DR) as a simulation platform for dose selection in tuberculosis vaccine trials. While the EMA appreciates the applicant's use of model-informed drug development and risk-based analysis, it notes that further clinical data and validation are necessary, particularly concerning the predictive value of interferon gamma as a biomarker in this setting. The letter encourages broader application and data collection to overcome current limitations and support future qualification.

The complete documentation of the two qualification advice procedures with the EMA is available in Open Access on Zenodo.

The complete documentation on the Qualification Advice with EMA for the BBCT-Hip solutions is here: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/10938447>.

The complete documentation on the Qualification Advice with EMA for the UISS-TB solution is here: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/10939450>.

4. DAT applications qualification strategies (UNICT, UNIBO)

4.1. Introduction

The Deep Accreditation Track (DAT) encompasses three solutions: UISS-MS, InSole, and AngioSupport. WP4 worked on the preparation of the preliminary regulatory strategies for each of the three DAT solutions, as reported in D4.3. Three validation collections, HFValid, StentValid and MSValid are also part of the process and are already available on the Zenodo In Silico World community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/insilicoworld-openaccess>). The ISW consortium has been undertaking the accreditation process for each of these solutions, with the potential for some to advance to the exploitation stage. Additionally, it aided in creating a legal and ethical inventory, establishing a framework of technical standards, providing a service for training surrogate models, and developing three application services.

4.2. UISS-MS qualification strategy

For its use as a pre-clinical design tool, UISS-MS requires no regulatory approval of any sort.

Before UISS-MS can be used by clinicians or pharmaceutical companies to provide personalised simulations, mirroring the course of the relapsing-remitting phase of MS or the effects of specific treatments based on individual clinical, laboratory, and MRI features, it would require regulatory approval. Unfortunately, the regulatory pathway is not easy to define. However, we agreed as follows.

UISS-MS can be used as:

1. A clinical decision support system (CDSS) that suggests the best treatment to reduce the multiple sclerosis disease progression in an individual patient or in a cohort of similar patients.
2. An In silico trial (IST) to predict the effect of new/existing drugs on a cohort of virtual patients to select the doses to be tested in phase II trials, or to predict drug efficacy in phase III trials.

In the first case, to be commercialised in the USA, the UISS-MS solution should be certified by the FDA as a Software as Medical Device (SaMD) with predictive capabilities. A recent guideline (<https://www.fda.gov/media/100714/download>) specifies that even for SaMD with predictive capabilities, credibility can be demonstrated following the technical standard ASME VV-40:2018.

To commercialise UISS-MS in the EU market, the pathway is very similar. While the ASME VV-40 is not an EU-harmonised standard, since an equivalent harmonised standard does not exist, the regulatory authorities should accept evidence of credibility obtained following the VV-40.

Thus, Mimesis S.r.l. and UNICT are recommended to explore designing a credibility analysis based on VV-40 for the UISS-MS solution when used as a clinical decision support system.

4.3. InSole qualification strategy

The regulatory pathway for custom orthotic devices via InSole software can be understood through five key questions:

1. Is the insole considered a medical device? It depends on the claims made; if it affects health, it's a medical device.
2. Which regulatory paths are suitable? Typically, it follows the custom-made device pathway.
3. Is an orthotic insole a custom-made device? If fitted by a qualified professional to meet individual needs, yes.

4. Can prefabricated insoles be marketed as medical devices? Yes, they can be CE marked, simplifying the custom-made device pathway.
5. What obligations do custom-made device manufacturers have? They must provide an Annex XIII statement and conduct post-market surveillance.

For the InSole solution, regulatory approval is required for patient-specific optimization. It is likely to be certified as a Software as Medical Device (SaMD) with predictive capabilities, with credibility demonstrated per ASME VV-40:2018. For commercialization, it is recommended to start with FDA guidelines for the US market, then seek CE marking for Europe, utilizing evidence from VV-40 for credibility analysis.

4.4. AngioSupport qualification strategy

AngioSupport can be certified either as a SaMD with predictive capabilities or as an MDDT, with the former being a preparatory step for both. It is recommended to certify AngioSupport first as medical device software for clinical decision support, then consider MDDT certification. Starting with FDA certification for the US market is advised, as it has established pathways. HeartFlow's experience suggests a complex FDA process, but a simpler 510k pathway might be possible. However, independent validation studies are crucial.

AngioSupport's complexity lies in its predictive capabilities and treatment support functions. Retrospective evidence like FAME1 study results might suffice for virtual FFR prediction but could be insufficient for treatment optimization claims. In Europe, there's no preventive qualification for MDDTs, unlike the FDA's process. Choosing the pathway depends on commercial prospects. Credibility assessment follows ASME VV-40:2018, necessitating a risk analysis and VVUQ plan, possibly using FAME1 data.

5. DAT Exploitation

UNICT has successfully licensed the UISS-MS solutions to MIM partners, enabling the provision of consulting services. These services offer two distinct business opportunities: support for pharmaceutical companies in the development of new treatments for Multiple Sclerosis (MS), and the facilitation of personalized therapy selection for MS patients in research hospitals through a Decision Support System. Additionally, IST has secured a license agreement to integrate the UISS-MS solution into the InSilicoTrials.com cloud-based platform under the name MS TreatSim (<https://insilicotrials.com/mstreatsim>), offering it as a web-based Software-as-a-Service (SaaS). This collaboration extends to consulting services for pharmaceutical companies in the development of MS treatments. Notably, UISS-MS has already been employed by two pharmaceutical companies. One utilized it to project the expanded usage of a specific drug in patients with relapsing-remitting MS for post-marketing regulatory documentation, while the other employed it to aid in the selection of indications and the design of a Phase II study.

Furthermore, UISS-TB has been made accessible to MIM partners for the provision of consultancy services related to tuberculosis therapies. Discussions are also underway with IST to potentially incorporate UISS-TB, along with tailored solutions for Influenza A and COVID-19, into the InSilicoVaccine Suite. This suite aims to combine immunoinformatic tools with predictions of immune system responses to support early vaccine design, disease progression simulations, and the evaluation of clinical efficacy using virtual populations.

UNIBO has entered into an agreement with IST at M33 for the commercialization of BBCT-Hip as a SaaS product on the InSilicoTrials.com platform. Integration efforts are underway, with the initial prototype of the cloud-based solution by M39.

Initially, the InSole solution has been utilized internally within the research and development department of RSP. Subsequently, it will be primarily targeted towards the podiatry market. Following internal use and further development, InSole technology will be commercialized as a software-as-a-service offering by RSP. It

will be integrated into the existing Footscan software as an additional module, rather than being sold separately.

The exploitation plan outlined in Deliverable D8.1 delineates the anticipated commercialization pathways for the most advanced computational solutions developed within the ISW project. These pathways include delivery as SaaS through the InSilicoTrials.com platform operated by IST, provision of consultancy services by MIM partners, or initial deployment as an internal research tool followed by incorporation into software features offered by RSP.

6. DMT applications qualification strategies (UNICT, UNIBO)

6.1. Introduction

The Deep Modelling Track (DMT) includes the following six solutions: ForceLoss, NeoIntima3D, UISS-MC, VirtualFD, OCDefects and UISS-COVID19. It was expected these solutions to complete the development stage and engage in the validation stage within the end of the project, thus producing three more validation collections (R14, R15, R17), and a service for sharing data (R32). WP4 worked on the preparation of the preliminary regulatory strategies for some of the most advanced DMT solutions: ForceLoss, UISS-MC, VirtualFD and OCDefects.

6.2. ForceLoss qualification strategy

The regulatory pathway for the ForceLoss solution is difficult to define, because contrary to most digital twins, ForceLoss does not predict quantities to be measured, but makes possible to tests if the measured values are compatible with a specific diagnosis. At the present level of understanding, for its use as a falsification tool to enable the stratification of patients, i.e. in the pre-enrollement phase of a clinical trial, the ForceLoss solution does not require any regulatory approval. The ForceLoss solution does not have a clinical use: its predictions are solely used to verify (test) the experimental findings (clinical hypotheses), not to inform clinical decision.

6.3. UISS-MC qualification strategy

For its use as a pre-clinical design tool, UISS-MC requires no regulatory approval of any sort.

Before UISS-MC can be used by clinicians or pharmaceutical companies to provide personalised simulations mirroring the effects of cancer-preventive vaccination protocols competitive with human-designed protocols, it must be qualified as medical product development tool Unfortunately, the regulatory pathway is not easy to define.

UISS-MC can be used as In Silico Trials for new medicinal therapies (which would also require EMA qualification) to predict the effect of new/existing drugs on a cohort of virtual patients to select the doses to be tested in phase II trials or to predict drug efficacy in phase III trials.

While the ASME VV-40 is not an EU-harmonised standard, since an equivalent harmonised standard does not exist, the regulatory authorities should accept evidence of credibility obtained following the VV-40.

Thus, Mimesis and UNICT are recommended to explore designing a credibility analysis based on VV-40 for the UISS-MC solution when used as an IST.

Summarising, at this stage UISS-MC owns a pre-clinical validation that is not sufficient for the EU market commercialization. It requires a dedicated regulatory pathway strategy that can lead to a qualification approval.

6.4. OcDefects qualification strategy

As indicated in the exploitation plan, the main use of for the OcDefects model for the foreseeable future is (early stage) research. Given the multiscale and multi-factorial nature of the model, it will serve the purpose of integrator of different observations at different length scales (organ, tissue, cell, intracellular) and will allow to increase understanding on the interplay between different (biological and mechanical) factors affecting the degeneration of osteochondral tissues. In terms of credibility assessment, verification of the individual elements and their links has been performed. For model validation, dedicated *in vitro* (microfluidics, spheroids etc., using human donor cells) and *in vivo* (mouse & rat) set-ups have been developed. In addition, clinical data is available in public databases such as the OA initiative. There are no immediate plans of moving the model from a research tool towards a medical device hence a full regulatory evaluation is not foreseen.

6.5. VirtualFD qualification strategy

VirtualFD, after certification, can be used as a decision support system; thus, first, it can be certified as a SaMD after full-scale validation and verification. Following the route of other companies in the field, 510K clearance from the FDA should be the first step. Next, an EMA qualification would be needed for different contexts of use.

First, to be used for In Silico trials, a specific context of use (according to ASME V&V40) shall be described for the population-specific question of interest.

Second, two questions of interest must be addressed to be used as a patient-specific decision support system. The first one must concern the patient-specific efficacy of deploying flow diverters. The second concern must address whether the former deployment scenario can reach an adequate outcome according to the surrogate clinical endpoint.

In summary, the credibility analysis based on the ASME V&V40 standard has to be performed individually for the context above of uses.

7. Concluding remarks (All)

This deliverable reports the final activities for the qualification advice process for FAT applications, thus closing one of the main WP4 milestones. Furthermore, qualification strategies for all DAT applications have been proposed and approved, and reports containing the fully detailed strategy have been shared on ISW's official common channels.